

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

MOOC

The Impact of International Migration on Remote Places

www.matilde-migration.eu

MATILDE has received
funding from the European
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research and innovation
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Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 7.8

MOOC on International Migration in Rural, Mountain Regions

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Matilde Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)

The Impact of International Migration on Remote Places

The MOOC on International Migration in Rural, Mountain Regions will offer a far-reaching training for young researchers, practitioners, journalists and NGO staff on the conceptual and policy-oriented results of MATILDE. It will be organized by BILGI. The MOOC will present the results of MATILDE conceptual elaborations and case studies to at least 100 participants.

Available at https://mooc.matilde-migration.eu/?_ga=2.57714858.1089242438.1656534699-1594931372.1616839119

Figure 1 Welcome screen of the MATILDE MOOC

Concept:

The MOOC on evaluating and enhancing the impact of international migration on rural and mountain areas will offer a far-reaching training on the **conceptual, methodological and policy-oriented results** of MATILDE. The Online Course is designed for anyone interested in regional development, rural and mountain areas as well as international (and even internal) migration. This may include **decision-makers, public, private and third sector development/migration agents, evaluators, facilitators, technical advisors, researchers, journalists, and students** involved in social innovation projects in rural areas or in the field of international migration.

Considering the goals of MATILDE, the MOOC aims to provide participants with interdisciplinary knowledge on the **social and economic impacts of migration**, with a special focus on their interactions with **territorial inequalities and spatial justice**. It will convey evidences and results that point to the **need for a regional approach to the governance of migration processes**. The Massive Open Online Course will aim **not only to inform** the participants regarding the main results of MATILDE, **but also to instruct** them to think locally; to underline that the place matters; and to recognize that the regional and local level needs to be taken into account during their future works, research and activities.

The course is free of charge and can be completed independently and asynchronously. Learners who pass the final exam will receive a Certificate of Attendance.

The language of instruction is English.

Structure:

The MOOC has a strong interdisciplinary approach as the one of MATILDE. The first part of the MOOC tackles the methodological and conceptual framework of the Project. However, before that, a first overview will be made on the key concepts of social, economic, and territorial impact. Indeed, we want to show how MATILDE has carried out its research, and what do we intend for an “impact” or an “assessment” within the socio, economic and territorial analysis of MATILDE. This first overview is certainly needed; and will be the preparatory framework to let students understand the main outcomes of MATILDE. Only after that, other transversal and more specific subjects might come into play.

Topics:

1. Introduction to the course programme
2. Rural and mountain areas of Europe: territorial inequalities and spatial justice
3. Migration patterns and migrants’ interactions with rural localities: conceptual thoughts towards a regional approach of migration impact assessment
4. Methodological and ethical aspects of research with migrants, and measuring the social impact
5. Measuring the economic impact: key concepts, dimensions and challenges
6. A Gender Perspective on the Economic and Social Impact of Migration
7. Communicative dialogical approach and best practices: MATILDE action research and participatory activities
8. Populism and citizenship in remote places
9. How can the post-Covid19 era foster a new attractiveness of internal regions?
10. Funds available

Requirements:

The MOOC consists of **10 units** or **20 hours**. It is open to students and non-students.

Participants are expected to read the required texts before class, follow the PPT Slides, and listen to the videos depicting the content of respective lecture. Students who have not completed these tasks will not have access to the following lecture's content.

Assessment: The participants who pass the final exam (a multiple-choice test) will be provided with a **Certificate of Attendance**. If the participant re-takes the test, the system will select a different set of questions.

Instructions:

- The course is available at
https://mooc.matilde-migration.eu/?_ga=2.57714858.1089242438.1656534699-1594931372.1616839119
- **Registration:** The participant must register with their personal data
- **Workload** consists of assigned readings, slides, videos to be followed, read, watched and processed. There are also suggestions of further reading material for those interested.
- **Online Exam:** When the participant completes the workload, s/he will be eligible to take the online exam composed of a set of 10 multiple choice questions
- **Certificate of Attendance:** Those who pass the test (minimum score 60 %) will receive the MATILDE MOOC Certificate of Attendance.